

Co-construction as key variable for effective educational landscapes

Marius Schwander & Stephan Gerhard Huber

To cite this article: Marius Schwander & Stephan Gerhard Huber (2025) Co-construction as key variable for effective educational landscapes, Cogent Education, 12:1, 2559162, DOI: [10.1080/2331186X.2025.2559162](https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2025.2559162)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2025.2559162>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 17 Sep 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 396

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Co-construction as key variable for effective educational landscapes

Marius Schwander^{a,b}

^aUniversity of Teacher Education Zug, Zug, Switzerland; ^bLinz School of Education, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Linz, Austria

ABSTRACT

School networks and educational landscapes have become established strategies for promoting innovations. Collaboration with extracurricular institutions expands the range of educational opportunities. This article examines how different forms of cooperation relate to benefits for professionals and students within the context of educational landscapes. Using latent change score models, we analyze the relationship between changes cooperation forms and associated outcomes over the course of a project. Data ($N = 197$) were collected at two time points for each cohort between 2014 and 2019 across 17 educational landscapes in Switzerland. Results indicate that co-construction is positively associated with emotional relief for professionals, as well as with improved focus on students reflecting an enhanced ability to address diverse learning needs. No positive associations were found between any form of cooperation and either workload reduction or professionalization. Nevertheless, educational landscapes may improve mutual understanding and foster a shared educational perspective, underscoring the importance of sufficient time for negotiation processes among actors from diverse professional backgrounds in building effective and sustainable cooperation.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 3 April 2025
Revised 22 July 2025
Accepted 12 August 2025

KEYWORDS

Educational landscapes; multi-professional cooperation; co-construction; teacher professional development; student learning progress

SUBJECTS

Social sciences; Education; Classroom practice; Assessment and testing; Teaching and learning

Introduction

The importance of teacher cooperation has grown significantly in recent years – both in research, particularly in the context of school and instructional quality, and in everyday school practice (Marty, 2022; Trumpa et al., 2016; Vangrieken et al., 2015). Professional learning communities (PLCs) enhance schools' capacity to respond to ongoing changes in educational policy and practice, and they support effective school development through the implementation of targeted programs (Moolenaar, 2010; Riveros et al., 2012; Tan & Caleon, 2016). The rise in teacher cooperation associated with PLCs has been empirically linked to teacher professionalization, improved instructional quality, and better school performance (Antinluoma et al., 2022; Beddoes et al., 2022; Latta, 2023; Lieberman & Mace, 2009; Servage, 2008; Vescio et al., 2008).

In recent years, to promote innovation in the education system and address complex educational and developmental challenges, schools have increasingly engaged in cross-sector collaborations (Berkemeyer et al., 2015; Huber et al., 2014; Koszuta et al., 2021; Muijs et al., 2010). These collaborations take shape in various domains: Inclusion and all-day school initiatives (Amrhein, 2014; Arnoldt, 2011; Trumpa et al., 2016) often require close cooperation with social and health professionals to ensure holistic student support. Such partnerships can improve access to non-academic services but frequently remain fragmented and dependent on individual school initiative (Bates et al., 2019; Bohnenkamp et al., 2023; Granrud et al., 2019; Ramukumba et al., 2019). In digital and distance learning, partnerships with instructional designers enhance teachers' technological competencies, enabling the creation of flexible, learner-centered environments that foster self-regulation and engagement of students (Abuhassna et al., 2024;

CONTACT Marius Schwander University of Teacher Education Zug, Zugerbergstrasse 3, 6300 Zug, Switzerland

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group
This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

Abuhassna & Alnawajha, 2023a, 2023b). Similarly, in STEAM education, collaborations in Communities of Practice including external experts from universities, industry, and creative sectors support interdisciplinary teaching and help bridge the gap between school and real-world contexts (Milara et al., 2020; Spyropoulou & Kameas, 2024; Z. Wu, 2022; Y. Wu et al., 2020). The involvement of extracurricular facilities creates new places of learning and a wider range of educational opportunities (Bastian, 2008; Koszuta et al., 2021) and is positively linked to better school performance, a reduction of socio-economic differences, lower drop-out rates and less absenteeism (Berkemeyer et al., 2015; Griffiths et al., 2021; Hillebrand et al., 2017).

As part of the 'Bildungslandschaften Schweiz' program, the Jacobs Foundation promotes structured collaboration between educational and non-educational actors. Local project coordinators facilitate this process by bringing together key stakeholders and organizing joint planning sessions, dialogue formats, and regular meetings. In such educational landscapes, professionals from different sectors work systematically across institutional boundaries to align their efforts and create coherent support structures—ultimately helping all children and young people access meaningful learning opportunities (Educational Landscapes Switzerland, 2017).

Although collaboration between school-based and external professionals is widely associated with positive outcomes for both students and practitioners, Griffiths et al. (2021) emphasize the lack of empirical studies that systematically examine these effects. While most studies on multi-professional cooperation are qualitative in nature, quantitative approaches on interprofessional collaboration are largely limited to the context of inclusive education within schools (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023). In contrast, Gräsel et al. (2006) distinguish between different forms of cooperation that provide a generally applicable framework and are also suitable for interdisciplinary collaboration between special education and general education teachers (Grosche et al., 2020). These forms serve distinct functions and are context-dependent, which has been empirically confirmed for structural conditions (Besa et al., 2024; Kalinowski et al., 2022) as well as outcome variables (Hartmann et al., 2021; Muckenthaler et al., 2019; Pozas & Letzel-Alt, 2023). However, empirical research has so far focused on teacher cooperation within schools, while studies on multi-professional collaboration with external stakeholders that differentiate between forms of cooperation are still lacking. This highlights a need for research that not only captures the complexity of collaborative processes but also tracks their development over time. To address this research gap, we pose the following research question: *Which forms of cooperation between school and non-school stakeholders promoted by educational landscapes are associated with which positive outcomes of cooperation for the involved stakeholders and students?*

This study seeks to address this research question by conducting one of the first quantitative, longitudinal analyses with a differentiated framework of cooperation between school-based and non-school actors within the framework of educational landscapes. Using latent change score modeling, we analyze longitudinal data collected through online surveys from participants in the 'Educational Landscapes Switzerland' project. Building on Gräsel and Fussangel's (2006) typology of cooperation, we adapt their framework to the context of multi-professional collaboration in educational landscapes. This methodological approach enables us to examine how different forms of cooperation are associated with specific positive outcomes for both practitioners and students. In doing so, the study contributes to theory development in the field of multi-professional collaboration in extracurricular educational settings. The findings aim to provide a foundation for reflection and evidence-based decision-making for educational policymakers and school leaders.

Theory and state of research

Based on the theory of forms of cooperation by Gräsel et al. (2006), Fussangel (2008) constructs the cooperation model, which assumes that the cooperation practice of teachers depends on certain framework conditions and that cooperation results in a number of positive outcomes for teachers, which ultimately have an impact on students (Moolenaar, 2010). With regard to the role of cooperation in connection with stress and burnout, reference is made to Böhm-Kasper's (2004) model. Specifically, emotional relief is expected through social support. Reference is also made to research on school development (team-building processes) and the effectiveness of schools (school culture, lesson

implementation, performance levels at class and teaching level). It is assumed that cooperating teachers are better able to adapt their lessons to the needs of the pupils. This subsumes professionalization through social and transformative learning (Lieberman & Mace, 2009; Putnam & Borko, 2000) on the one hand and more student-centered teaching on the other (Fend, 2006).

Building on this model, we develop differentiated hypotheses to examine whether and how the three types of cooperation are associated with distinct outcome dimensions. To date, however, most studies conceptualize cooperation in a general sense, without distinguishing between specific forms of collaboration. This limits our understanding of how different cooperation types may relate to particular outcomes, as suggested by Fussangel's (2008) framework. The following section discusses the current state of research regarding the anticipated effects of teacher and multi-professional cooperation in this context.

Although collaboration among teachers can initially lead to an increased workload (Luder et al., 2017; Vangrieken et al., 2015), it is expected that the benefits outweigh any potential drawbacks (Steinert & Maag Merki, 2009) and ultimately *reduce workload* in the long term (Fussangel & Gräsel, 2012) – a finding supported by empirical studies (Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Vangrieken et al., 2015). Similar results have been found for multi-professional collaboration: it offers relief through resource pooling, division of labor, and enhanced support (Maykus, 2009a). However, these benefits cannot be clearly attributed to specific forms of collaboration: while division of labor suggests synchronized cooperation, support may also arise from mere exchange without deeper coordination.

Through the relieving discussions associated with collaboration, teachers receive socio-emotional support, feel less isolated, report lower stress levels, greater well-being, and higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation (Berkemeyer et al., 2013; Griffiths et al., 2021; Halbheer et al., 2008; Muckenthaler et al., 2019, 2020; Steinert & Maag Merki, 2009; Vangrieken et al., 2015). While *emotional relief* such supportive conversations can occur across all forms of collaboration – whether among teachers or in multi-professional teams – it remains unclear which forms of cooperation are more or less conducive to fostering them.

According to social learning theory, professional learning groups offer valuable opportunities for the exchange of ideas and joint reflection on pedagogical practices, enabling teachers to expand their instructional repertoire (Fussangel, 2008; Putnam & Borko, 2000). Empirical studies show that professional learning groups foster transformative learning, generate new knowledge and beliefs, and enhance professional development, instructional effectiveness, and innovation (Holzberger & Schiepe-Tiska, 2021; Lieberman & Mace, 2009; Maag Merki & Steinert, 2006; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Vescio et al., 2008; Watkins, 2016). Similar findings have been reported in the context of multi-professional collaboration: engaging with unfamiliar practices and perspectives in school networks encourages participants to question established routines and beliefs, thereby promoting mutual learning and professional growth (Berkemeyer et al., 2013; Maykus, 2009b). Inter-school and cross-institutional networks have been shown to influence teaching practices, school development, and evaluation (Bielefeldt et al., 1999; Dederling, 2007; Earl et al., 2006; Harris et al., 2006), and to improve skills, motivation, and understanding in areas such as inclusive education (Bell et al., 2006; Jopling, 2005). These effects are further supported by recent studies showing that collaboration with professionals from other contexts – whether through informal learning (Baldwin et al., 2018) or targeted didactic interventions (An et al., 2022) – can enhance professional competencies. In fields like STEAM education, external partnerships have proven particularly valuable in fostering interdisciplinary learning and supporting the implementation of innovative practices (Milara et al., 2020; Spyropoulou & Kameas, 2024; Z. Wu, 2022; Y. Wu et al., 2020). Taken together, these findings suggest that the underlying learning mechanisms in both teacher and multi-professional collaboration are largely co-constructive in nature. However, the acquisition of content knowledge may also result from the mere exchange of new materials or perspectives, without necessarily involving deeper collaborative engagement.

An *enhanced student focus* refers to teachers' improved ability to respond to the specific learning needs of their students, thereby contributing to better student outcomes (Fussangel, 2008). More student-centered teaching strategies and a shift toward collective responsibility for student success and educational equity have been identified as key outcomes of collaborative practices (Berkemeyer et al., 2013; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Slavit et al., 2011; Vangrieken et al., 2015). These effects are evident

not only in teacher collaboration but also in multi-professional cooperation: Multi-professional collaboration – whether with external experts from education, health, and social services or with parents – has been shown to improve the coordination and accessibility of support services, foster more opportunities to address vulnerable groups of learners, more comprehensive and individualized support planning and improved implementation of interventions, as well as more individualized and technology-supported learning environments (Abuhassna & Alnawajha, 2023a, 2023b; Ainscow et al., 2006; Bates et al., 2019; Griffiths et al., 2021; Muijs et al., 2010). Moreover, it contributes to improved self-regulation and motivation of the students, improved academic performance, particularly for vulnerable student groups, social-emotional development, smoother educational transitions, higher employment rates, and reduced absenteeism and dropout rates (Adler et al., 1995; Ainscow et al., 2006; Berkemeyer et al., 2015; Cummings et al., 2007; Hord, 1997; Jopling, 2005; Muijs et al., 2010; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Zetlin et al., 1998). However, the findings remain inconclusive regarding which specific forms of collaboration are particularly conducive to promoting student-related outcomes.

Professional exchange facilitates access to relevant information and materials through the mutual offering and seeking of advice and support (Gräsel et al., 2006; Rosenholtz, 2000), which can provide both practical and emotional relief (Wilbers, 2004). In contrast, exchange has not been found to promote the implementation of differentiated instruction (Pozas & Letzel-Alt, 2023). We therefore hypothesize that *professional exchange in multi-professional settings is positively associated with workload reduction and emotional relief, but not with professionalization or an improved focus on students (Hypothesis 1)*.

Joint work organization based on a division of labor enables teachers to complete shared tasks—such as preparing and correcting teaching units and assessments—more efficiently, particularly when working with students with special needs (Fussangel & Gräsel, 2012; Gräsel et al., 2006; Grosche et al., 2020; Richter & Pant, 2016; Tjosvold et al., 2003). Moreover, synchronization has been identified as the strongest predictor of teachers' implementation of differentiated instruction (Pozas & Letzel-Alt, 2023). Based on these findings, we hypothesize that *joint work organization in multi-professional settings is positively associated with reduced workload and an improved focus on students, but not with emotional relief or professionalization (Hypothesis 2)*.

Co-construction involves jointly planning, implementing, and reflecting on teaching to develop shared solutions for complex challenges (Grosche et al., 2020). It fosters content knowledge, evidence-based practice, and the development of new solutions through situational learning and the integration of diverse perspectives – benefiting both regular and special education teachers (Fischer, 2002; Grosche et al., 2020; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Plauborg, 2009; Putnam & Borko, 2000; Zech et al., 2000). Co-construction supports instructional innovation, strengthens inclusive mindsets, and enhances teachers' focus on students and their needs. It is also positively associated with the implementation of differentiated instruction and effective educational improvements (Grosche et al., 2020; J. W. Little, 2003; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Pool Maag, 2022; Pozas & Letzel-Alt, 2023; Richter & Pant, 2016; Thomas et al., 1998). We therefore hypothesize that *co-construction in multi-professional settings is positively associated with workload reduction, emotional relief, professionalization, and an improved focus on students (Hypothesis 3)*.

Method

Sample and procedure

The data was collected in two phases as part of an initiative to network school and extracurricular stakeholders in educational landscapes in Switzerland (initial surveys: February 2014 and October 2015; final surveys: November/December 2016 and between October 2018 and February 2019). Prior to each survey wave, coordinators were asked to provide a list of current members of their educational landscapes. These individuals were then invited to take part in the online survey via personalized links. The response rate was slightly over 40 percent ($0.41 \leq p \leq 0.44$).

Longitudinal studies inevitably involve non-response and participant drop-out. Cases with data from only one measurement point were excluded from the dataset. Additionally, educational landscapes with fewer than four respondents were removed. The final sample comprises $N = 197$ individuals from 17

Table 1. Confirmatory factor analysis of forms of cooperation.

Model	AIC	BIC	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA
1	2839.00	2942.51	82.10	51	1.61	0.92	0.90	0.07	0.08
2a	2838.77	2944.93	80.40	50	1.61	0.92	0.90	0.07	0.08
2b	2823.14	2929.30	67.31	50	1.35	0.96	0.94	0.06	0.06
3	2819.05	2930.52	61.35	48	1.28	0.97	0.95	0.06	0.05

Note: Model 1 includes a single factor. Model 2a distinguishes between one factor for professional exchange and another for items related to joint work organization and co-construction. Model 2b combines items on professional exchange and joint work organization into one factor, with a separate factor for co-construction. Model 3 specifies a separate factor for each form of cooperation.

educational landscapes located in five German-speaking and three French-speaking cantons in Switzerland. Attrition analyses based on demographic variables and motivational aspects (see [Appendix](#)) revealed no evidence of bias due to sample drop-outs (Eisner et al., 2019) or the use of standard FIML imputation to address missing data (Buuren, 2018).

Instruments

In our study, we use the types of cooperation according to Fussangel (2008). The wording of the items was adapted to the educational landscape context. Confirmatory factor analyses were conducted for models with 1, 2 or 3 factors (see [Table 1](#)). The fit indices support the 3-factor solution with the dimensions Professional exchange (e.g. 'I exchange working documents with colleagues in the Educational Landscapes project'), Joint work organization (e.g. 'I create working materials (information letters, flyers, teaching course materials, etc.) with colleagues in the educational landscape project'), and co-construction (e.g. 'I carry out joint activities (courses, special events, sub-projects, etc.) with colleagues in the educational landscapes project'), with four items each.

To determine the benefits arising from networking and cooperation in the educational context, we rely on the operationalization of Fussangel (2008). Wording of the four dimensions workload reduction, emotional relief, professionalization and improved focus on students was adapted to educational landscapes. The dimension of work relief with three negatively coded items (e.g. 'Cooperation with colleagues in the educational landscape is associated with greater effort compared to individual work') achieved insufficient internal consistencies (see [Table 3](#)) but kept in our study due to the theoretical framework. To capture emotional relief (e.g. 'I can have open conversations with colleagues in the educational landscape that take the pressure off me'), we added a fourth items, asking whether colleagues in the educational landscape from other organizations experienced similar problems. Professional benefit (e.g. 'I can benefit professionally from the experience of my colleagues in the educational landscape') was measured with three items, omitting the item on support for their own lesson preparation. Improved Focus on Students was captured with four items (e.g. 'The learning and development processes of children and young people are better promoted through cooperation in the educational landscape'). The item about standards in relation to student performance was changed to common principles for dealing with students, to better match our context.

Items of all subscales were rated on a 4-point response scale from 1 = 'strongly disagree' to 4 = 'strongly agree'.

The test for measurement invariance across time points shows scalar measurement invariance for all dimensions (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002) and is presented in the [Appendix](#).

Models of analysis

In line with the programmatic logic underlying the data context—namely, that cooperation is expected to be initiated and supported through coordinated local action—we focus on changes in cooperation and their potential positive outcomes from the first measurement point at the initiation of the educational landscape projects to the last measurement point at the end of the funded project phase. For this purpose, latent change score models (LCSM) were calculated (McArdle et al., 2000), which use different strengths of latent growth curve models and autoregressive cross-lagged models (Clark et al., 2018; Grimm et al., 2017; Matusik et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020). This modeling approach allows for the direct

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of initial and final survey (manifest).

	Initial survey		Final survey	
	M	SD	M	SD
Professional exchange	3.08	0.74	3.08	0.59
Joint work organization	2.60	0.88	2.82	0.85
Co-construction	2.60	0.85	2.61	0.70
Reduced workload	2.55	0.62	2.74	0.59
Emotional relief	2.95	0.74	2.91	0.69
Professionalization	3.24	0.58	3.22	0.67
Improved focus on students	3.28	0.56	3.20	0.58

Note: M = mean, SD = standard deviation. All items were answered on a 4-point likert scale from 1 = «does not apply at all» to 4 = «fully applies».

Table 3. Bivariate Pearson correlations and Cronbach's alpha.

Dimension	Initial survey							Final survey						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Professional exchange (1)	$\alpha = 0.87$							$\alpha = 0.74$						
Joint work organization (2)	0.66**	$\alpha = 0.88$						0.50**	$\alpha = 0.86$					
Co-construction (3)	0.73**	0.71**	$\alpha = 0.82$					0.62**	0.73**	$\alpha = 0.70$				
Reduced workload (4)	0.24**	0.24**	0.22**	$\alpha = 0.54$				0.01	-0.07	0.01	$\alpha = 0.53$			
Emotional relief (5)	0.32**	0.32**	0.40**	0.21**	$\alpha = 0.72$			0.39**	0.20*	0.40**	0.12	$\alpha = 0.76$		
Professionalization (6)	0.38**	0.35**	0.32**	0.22**	0.54**	$\alpha = 0.80$		0.40**	0.23*	0.36**	0.16*	0.62**	$\alpha = 0.85$	
Improved focus on students (7)	0.35**	0.30**	0.41**	0.12	0.52**	0.50**	$\alpha = 0.84$	0.39**	0.08	0.25**	-0.04	0.43**	0.55**	$\alpha = 0.76$

Note: Significance levels: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

estimation of intraindividual change and is particularly suitable for studying developmental dynamics, intervention effects, and potential couplings between change processes in different constructs (Howardson et al., 2017; Lucas, 2023; Zainal & Newman, 2021). Unlike traditional growth models, LCSM can be estimated with as few as two measurement occasions, provided there is a strong theoretical foundation (Cáncer et al., 2021). While this limits the ability to model nonlinear trajectories or assess the stability of change, it still enables the estimation of associations between latent change variables. In the growth model of the LCSM, the autoregressive paths are fixed at 1 so that the residual explains the change. In the structural model, the changes of the outcome dimensions are regressed on the change of cooperation. By modeling change at the latent level, it allows for the control of measurement error, which is particularly beneficial given our relatively small sample size, as it helps to improve the precision of parameter estimates and reduces the risk of biased conclusions due to unreliability in observed indicators (T. D. Little, 2013). However, due to the limited sample size, a separate model was calculated for each type of cooperation as predictor.

Results

Our descriptive results show higher means for exchange than for co-construction (see Table 2), which aligns with previous findings (Besa et al., 2024; Hartmann et al., 2021; Kalinowski et al., 2022; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Richter & Pant, 2016; Terhart & Klieme, 2006; Vangrieken et al., 2015). The correlations (see Table 3) among the types of cooperation indicate distinct constructs, justifying a nuanced analysis (see Gräsel et al., 2006; Hartmann et al., 2021; Kalinowski et al., 2022).

Results of the LCS-Models for each type of cooperation are shown in Table 4. All models achieved good fit according to common criteria (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The models for professional exchange ($\chi^2 = 219.06$, $df = 35$, $p < 0.001$, CFI = 0.98, TLI = 0.95, SRMR = 0.09, RMSEA = 0.04) and joint work organization ($\chi^2 = 194.99$, $df = 35$, $p < 0.001$, CFI = 0.98, TLI = 0.94, SRMR = 0.09, RMSEA = 0.04) show no significant paths on any dependent variable. While the absence of effects on professionalization and improved focus on students is consistent with our hypothesis, the lack of association between professional exchange and both workload reduction and emotional relief contradicts Hypothesis 1. Similarly, although the absence of effects on emotional relief and professionalization aligns with our expectations, the missing link between joint work organization and both workload reduction and an improved focus on students contradicts Hypothesis 2. However, in the model of joint work organization,

Table 4. Latent change score-models.

Model	Dependent variable	β	SE	p	R^2	Hypothesis test
Professional Exchange	Reduced workload	0.080	0.143	0.578	0.006	✗
	Emotional relief	0.053	0.173	0.761	0.003	✗
	Professionalization	-0.002	0.131	0.988	0.000	✓
	Improved focus on students	-0.002	0.176	0.990	0.000	✓
Joint Work Organization	Reduced workload	0.000	0.212	0.999	0.000	✗
	Emotional relief	0.072	0.155	0.643	0.005	✓
	Professionalization	-0.105	0.132	0.427	0.011	✓
	Improved focus on students	0.192	0.144	0.183	0.037	(✓)
Co-construction	Reduced workload	0.132	0.170	0.438	0.017	✗
	Emotional relief	0.349	0.152	0.022	0.122	✓
	Professionalization	-0.065	0.121	0.592	0.004	✗
	Improved focus on students	0.141	0.065	0.030	0.020	✓

the standardized regression coefficient and explained variance for improved focus on students – though not statistically significant¹ – correspond to small effects ($f = 0.04$) according to Cohen (1988), which is consistent with Hypothesis 2. The model for co-construction ($\chi^2 = 203.56$, $df = 35$, $p < 0.001$, CFI = 0.98, TLI = 0.97, SRMR = 0.08, RMSEA = 0.03) shows no significant paths on both workload reduction and professionalization, which is not consistent with hypothesis 3. The model shows a significant correlation between the change in co-construction during the project phase and change in the assessment for both improved focus on students as well as emotional relief, which is consistent with hypothesis 3. The standardized regression coefficient for emotional relief corresponds to a medium effect. However, the variance explanation corresponds to a small effect for both emotional relief ($f = 0.13$) and improved focus on students ($f = 0.02$). Overall, our hypotheses were only partially confirmed (see Table 4).

Discussion

The aim of our study was to test the theoretical model of cooperation, which assumes that different forms of cooperation serve different functions and purposes (Fussangel, 2008; Gräsel et al., 2006). We analyzed data from educational landscapes projects in Switzerland (Huber et al., 2021; Koszuta et al., 2021) using LCSM. In the following, we discuss our findings on workload reduction, emotional relief, professionalization, and improved focus on students for each of the three forms of cooperation, in light of existing research.

Contrary to our hypothesis, our data do not support any relationship between *professional exchange* and both workload reduction and emotional relief for participants in the educational landscapes. According to our findings, the exchange of relevant or helpful information and materials (Gräsel et al., 2006) and seeking and offering advice and support (Rosenholtz, 2000) among members of the educational landscape do not lead to the expected relieving effects. The absence of a relationship between professional exchange and improved focus on students is consistent with our hypothesis, as previous findings also suggest that it does not promote the implementation of differentiated instruction (Pozas & Letzel-Alt, 2023).

Our data do not indicate any significant relationship between *joint work organization* and positive outcomes for participants in the educational landscapes. For emotional relief and professionalization – for which no effects were expected – the results align with our hypothesis. However, the absence of an effect on workload reduction contradicts our expectations and challenges the assumption that this is the primary function of this form of cooperation (Gräsel et al., 2006; Tjosvold et al., 2003). Organizing and structuring work collaboratively can be challenging for teachers accustomed to individual planning. Yet, when successfully implemented, it may ease the workload and increase efficiency in everyday school life (Fussangel & Gräsel, 2012). This may also apply to multi-professional cooperation, which in this case may not have been effectively established. Alternatively, in cross-professional collaboration, joint work organization might not lead to time savings due to the inherently separate nature of tasks. Also contrary to our hypothesis, no significant effect was found for joint work organization on improved focus on students. However, the standardized regression coefficient and explained variance suggest a small effect that may not have reached significance due to the limited sample size. This finding aligns with previous research identifying synchronization as the strongest predictor of differentiated instruction (Pozas & Letzel-Alt, 2023). It is also possible that when goals in educational landscapes cannot be achieved

individually (Gräsel et al., 2006), actors from different professions tend to engage in co-construction instead of joint work organization. This seems particularly plausible given that the development of new educational offerings was a central focus in these educational landscapes (Koszuta et al., 2021). A discussion of the results on co-construction follows below.

Although the *co-construction* type of cooperation is very time-consuming (Gräsel et al., 2006; Grosche et al., 2020), especially at the beginning, we assumed it would lead to a reduction in workload and emotional relief for those involved throughout the project. Contrary to our hypothesis, co-construction and reflection do not significantly impact workload reduction, showing at best a negligible effect. However, consistent with our hypothesis, a moderate correlation between co-construction and emotional relief was found, though only a small portion of the variance in emotional relief could be explained, suggesting that it depends significantly on other factors. According to previous research, the challenging initial phase must be overcome with motivation to achieve long-term benefits like reduced workload and positive emotional and motivational effects (Fussangel & Dizinger, 2014; Gräsel et al., 2006; Grosche et al., 2020; Muckenthaler et al., 2020). Consistent with this, a change in co-constructive processes in educational landscapes seemed to contribute to emotional relief over the project's duration, albeit to a limited extent. However, coordinating the work of different professions seems too demanding, or it may be practically impossible to align work segments in a way that achieves workload reduction.

We followed the assumption, that co-construction as an intensive form of cooperation, including joint planning, implementation, and reflection, lead to both professionalization and a better focus on the needs and learning success of all students. Contrary to our hypothesis, our findings don't support a connection between co-construction and the professionalization of the project partners in educational landscapes. This contradicts previous research which states that reflective practice and the integration of different perspectives within the collaborative process enable the development of new solutions beyond existing knowledge and skills, while also enhancing the professional practice for different professions (Fischer, 2002; Gräsel et al., 2006; Grosche et al., 2020; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Wood, 2007). In contrast, in line with our hypothesis, our findings support the fact that co-construction in the educational landscapes contribute to an improved focus on students, albeit to a limited extent. This aligns with existing research suggesting that co-construction fosters a shared understanding and a sense of responsibility for all students, while also enhancing the ability to address the students' needs and support their development (Grosche et al., 2020; J. W. Little, 2003; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Richter & Pant, 2016). However, empirical evidence on student performance suggests that only collaboration during planning – rather than other reflective aspects of co-construction – significantly predicts student achievement (Reeves et al., 2017). The measurement of co-construction, consisting different aspects, may partly explain the low observed effect. A more differentiated analysis using refined instruments could therefore be warranted.

Our data did not support any effects of multi-professional cooperation within the educational landscape on either workload reduction or the professionalization of the partners during the project phase. This may be due to the involvement of different professional groups, suggesting that cooperation might not have the same impact on these two variables as is known from teacher cooperation within schools (cf. Fischer, 2002; Fussangel & Dizinger, 2014; Fussangel & Gräsel, 2012; Gräsel et al., 2006; Grosche et al., 2020; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Wood, 2007), or at least they don't experience it. We found significant small to moderate effects for co-construction on emotional relief and improved focus on students and additionally a tendency but insignificant effect of joint work organization on improved student. At least the main focus of the educational landscape project – to increase opportunities for high-quality education for all students (Koszuta et al., 2021) – appears to be supported by the reported improvements in student focus. Similarly, the reported emotional relief suggests that the participants likely had a generally positive experience and did not express notable dissatisfaction (cf. Besa et al., 2024; Luder et al., 2017; Steinert & Maag Merki, 2009). These developments seem to have been facilitated, at least in part, by the co-constructive collaboration among the involved partners. However, given that most found effects remain small, these findings should be interpreted with caution and not overstated in terms of their practical impact.

Limitation and further research perspectives

Although the data used is somewhat aged, it contributes to closing the research gap regarding the context sensitivity of different types of cooperation within educational landscapes. Findings on networking with extracurricular partners remain highly relevant for school development and the implementation of innovations – particularly in addressing diversity and bridging achievement gaps among students from different socio-economic backgrounds (Berkemeyer et al., 2013; Hillebrand et al., 2017; Lütje-Klose & Urban, 2014; Muckenthaler et al., 2020; Muijs, 2015).

However, the study is subject to several limitations that should be addressed in future research. The limited number of educational landscapes and actors involved reflects the pilot character of the initiative and the fact that many landscapes were still in early development stages. In addition, the complexity of the evaluation process may have discouraged broader participation, contributing to a smaller sample size and turnover. Although attrition analyses suggest that systematic distortions due to high fluctuation in the projects (Eisner et al., 2019) are unlikely, the dynamic nature of such initiatives may still affect the generalizability of findings. In addition, the statistical power of our analyses was limited, which further restricts the generalizability of the results.

Considering moderating support conditions (see Muckenthaler et al., 2020) such as available time frames (see McCullum, 2017) or administrative support (e.g. Kilbane, 2009; Olivier & Huffman, 2016; Thompson & McKelvy, 2007) as well as a more nuanced analysis of the initiation, implementation, and integration phase of projects (see Leclerc et al., 2012) could provide deeper insights into the mechanisms that foster or hinder sustainable collaboration in educational landscapes. Future studies should therefore aim to include larger samples with several measuring points that allow longitudinal designs that can account for dynamic participation patterns, such as multiphase growth models (Reinecke & Seddig, 2011). These approaches may help to better capture the evolving nature of cooperation processes and mitigate the impact of participant turnover. Moreover, the exploratory findings reported here should be replicated in studies with larger samples to validate and extend the present insights.

Implication for practice

The present study – as one of the first empirical longitudinal studies in the field of multiprofessional cooperation between school-based and external professionals – shows that cooperation on a higher level, namely co-construction fosters an improved focus on students, which is consistent with previous claims in fostering teacher cooperation (Berkemeyer et al., 2013; Muckenthaler et al., 2020) and cooperation with external partners (Abuhassna & Alnawajha, 2023a; Ainscow et al., 2006; Muijs et al., 2010). It also shows that co-construction also pays off for teachers and other professionals, which is consistent with previous findings on teacher cooperation to provide emotional relief (Gräsel et al., 2006; Muckenthaler et al., 2020).

The evidence-based indication of effects for both professionals and students should serve as a strong incentive for school leaders, network coordinators and educational policymakers in different contexts to actively promote co-constructive cooperation between school-based and non-school-based professionals. This can be achieved through structured, school-based team approaches (Bates et al., 2019) and by providing both content-related and organizational support for planning and facilitating structured exchange formats, similar to the well-documented role of school leadership in fostering teacher collaboration (Anderegg, 2019; Kalinowski et al., 2022; van Schaik et al., 2020; Warwas et al., 2019; Zhang & Zheng, 2020). The targeted coordination of cooperation meetings and support by a local based manager or a management committee can strengthen cooperation between educational professionals and, in particular, promote the active involvement and influence of non-school partners in educational networks (Coelen et al., 2022; Järvinen et al., 2015; Koranyi & Kolleck, 2017; Koszuta, 2025).

Conclusion

We found no effects for 'lower' forms of cooperation, but weak associations for co-construction—specifically with emotional relief and improved focus on students, though not with professionalization. Whether these results are specific to the context of multi-professional cooperation in extracurricular

settings, or simply reflect the generally mixed findings in related research on teacher collaboration (Besa et al., 2024; Massenkeil & Rothland, 2016) or school-to-school cooperation (Muijs, 2015) remains an open question. Analogous to Muijs' conclusion, cooperation within educational landscapes also appears to be a time- and effort-intensive process that depends on a range of conditions and does not always succeed, highlighting the need for further research.

From our perspective, educational landscapes offer considerable potential to foster sustainable cooperation between school-based and non-school-based actors (Lehmpfuhl & Pfeiffer, 2008; Lohre, 2007; Minderop & Solzbacher, 2007) and should therefore be further supported. While this view goes beyond the scope of our empirical findings, it aligns with prior work emphasizing the crucial role of sufficient time resources to build mutual commitment and maintain continuity in multi-professional collaborations (Arnoldt, 2011; Santen & Seckinger, 2003; Thielen, 2010).

Note

1. We interpret effect sizes (without generalizing) due to the low statistical power resulting from the small sample size. This increases the likelihood of Type II errors – that is, failing to detect true effects in the population (Neyman & Pearson, 1928).

Acknowledgements

Generative AI tools (ChatGPT, Copilot, DeepL) were used to support translation, rephrasing, and language refinement of selected passages written by the authors of this paper; all outputs were carefully reviewed and edited to ensure accuracy and originality.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This paper is based on data collected by the project Educational Landscapes Switzerland [Reference Number 2012 996] supported by the Jacobs Foundation.

About the authors

Marius Schwander is a doctoral candidate in the PhD Program in Education at the Linz School of Education, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria. With an academic background in social and business psychology (MSc), his research focuses on the scientific monitoring of educational projects and initiatives using quantitative methods. His thematic interests include cooperation, leadership, person–organization fit, and well-being. The present article is part of the cumulative dissertation and conceptualized, conducted, and written by him.

Prof. Dr. Stephan Gerhard Huber holds the Chair of Excellence for Leadership, Quality Management and Innovation and is Head of the Center for Education Leadership and Management at the Johannes Kepler University Linz (Austria), Head of the working group on Personnel, Organization and Systems Development at the Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education (IPN) Kiel/Berlin (Germany), and Head of the Institute for Educational Quality and Innovation (Switzerland). He was responsible for acquiring and leading the research project from which the data used in this article originate.

ORCID

Marius Schwander <http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2537-2229>

Stephan Gerhard Huber <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6458-9163>

References

- Abuhassna, H., Adnan, M. A. B. M., & Awae, F. (2024). Exploring the synergy between instructional design models and learning theories: A systematic literature review. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 16(2), ep499. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/14289>

- Abuhassna, H., & Alnawajha, S. (2023a). Instructional design made easy! Instructional design models, categories, frameworks, educational context, and recommendations for future work. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 13(4), 715–735. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe13040054>
- Abuhassna, H., & Alnawajha, S. (2023b). The transactional distance theory and distance learning contexts: Theory integration, research gaps, and future agenda. *Education Sciences*, 13(2), 112. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13020112>
- Adler, L., Cragin, J., & Searls, P. (1995). *The Los Angeles area business/education partnership. A study of the impact of a community based school to work program for high risk youth*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED388851>
- Ainscow, M., Muijs, D., & West, M. (2006). Collaboration as a strategy for improving schools in challenging circumstances. *Improving Schools*, 9(3), 192–202. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480206069014>
- Amrhein, B. (2014). Inklusive Bildungslandschaften: Neue Anforderungen an die Professionalisierung von Schulleitungen. In S. G. Huber (Ed), *Jahrbuch Schulleitung 2014*. Carl Link Verlag.
- An, H., Sung, W., & Yoon, S. Y. (2022). Implementation of learning by design in a synchronized online environment to teach educational robotics to inservice teachers. *Educational Technology Research and Development: ETR & D*, 70(4), 1473–1496. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-022-10134-8>
- Anderegg, N. (2019). Auf die Schulleitung kommt es an!: Schweizer Perspektive auf den Zusammenhang zwischen Schulführung und Inklusion. In J. Donlic, E. Jaksche-Hoffman, & H. K. Peterlini (Hrsg.), *Ist inklusive Schule möglich?* (S. 111–132). transcript Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783839443125-007>
- Antinluoma, M., Ilomäki, L., & Toom, A. (2022). The involvement of teaching assistants in professional learning communities. *Cogent Education*, 9(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2022.2145811>
- Arnoldt, B. (2011). Kooperation zwischen Ganztagschule und außerschulischen Partnern. Entwicklung der Rahmenbedingungen. In N. Fischer, H. G. Holtappels, E. Klieme, T. Rauschenbach, L. Stecher, & I. Züchner (Hrsg.), *Ganztagschule: Entwicklung, Qualität, Wirkungen. Längsschnittliche Befunde der Studie zur Entwicklung von Ganztagschulen (StEG)* (S. 312–329). Beltz Juventa. <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0111-pedocs-192012>
- Baldwin, S. J., Ching, Y.-H., & Friesen, N. (2018). Online course design and development among college and university instructors: An analysis using grounded theory. *Online Learning*, 22(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v22i2.1212>
- Bastian, J. (2008). In regionalen Bildungsnetzwerken lernen. Fragen für die Praxis. *Pädagogik*, 60(7/8), 6–11.
- Bates, S. M., Mellin, E., Paluta, L. M., Anderson-Butcher, D., Vogeler, M., & Sterling, K. (2019). Examining the influence of interprofessional team collaboration on student-level outcomes through school–community partnerships. *Children & Schools*, 41(2), 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cs/cdz001>
- Beddoes, Z., Sazama, D., & Starck, J. (2022). “I wish I had had you as a PE teacher”: Physical educators’ experiences in a professional learning community. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 41(1), 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2020-0177>
- Bell, M., Jopling, M., Cordingley, P., Firth, A., King, E., & Mitchell, H. (2006). What is the impact on pupils of networks that include at least three schools? What additional benefits are there for practitioners, organisations and the communities they serve? National College for School Leadership.
- Berkemeyer, N., Bos, W., Järvinen, H., Manitius, V., & Holt, N. V. (2015). *Netzwerkbasierter Unterrichtsentwicklung. Ergebnisse der wissenschaftlichen Begleitforschung zum Projekt „Schulen im Team“*. Waxmann.
- Berkemeyer, N., Järvinen, H., Otto, J., & Bos, W. (2013). Kooperation und Reflexion als Strategien der Professionalisierung in schulischen Netzwerken. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogik*, 57, 225–247.
- Besa, K.-S., Gesang, J., Kruse, C., & Rothland, M. (2024). Voraussetzungen für und Bedeutung von unterschiedlichen Kooperationsformen als Quelle der Arbeitszufriedenheit und Mitarbeiterbindung von Lehrkräften. *Gruppe. Interaktion. Organisation. Zeitschrift für Angewandte Organisationspsychologie (GIO)*, 55(1), 69–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11612-024-00723-x>
- Bielefeldt, T., Moursund, D., Underwood, S., & Underwood, D. (1999). *Connected learning communities: Findings from the road ahead program, 1995-1997*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED429585>
- Böhm-Kasper, O. (2004). *Schulische Belastung und Beanspruchung* (D. H. Rost, Hrsg.; Bd. 43). Waxmann Verlag.
- Bohnenkamp, J. H., Patel, C., Connors, E., Orenstein, S., Ereshefsky, S., Lever, N., & Hoover, S. (2023). Evaluating strategies to promote effective, multidisciplinary team collaboration in school mental health. *Journal of Applied School Psychology*, 39(2), 130–150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15377903.2022.2077875>
- Buuren, S. V. (2018). *Flexible imputation of missing data* (2. Aufl.). Chapman and Hall/CRC. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780429492259>
- Cáncer, P. F., Estrada, E., Ollero, M. J. F., & Ferrer, E. (2021). Dynamical properties and conceptual interpretation of latent change score models. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 696419. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.696419>
- Chen, F. F. (2007). Sensitivity of goodness of fit indexes to lack of measurement invariance. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 14(3), 464–504. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705510701301834>
- Cheung, G. W., & Rensvold, R. B. (2002). Evaluating goodness-of-fit indexes for testing measurement invariance. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 9(2), 233–255. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15328007SEM0902_5
- Clark, D. A., Nuttall, A. K., & Bowles, R. P. (2018). Misspecification in latent change score models: consequences for parameter estimation, model evaluation, and predicting change. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, 53(2), 172–189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00273171.2017.1409612>

- Coelen, T., Hemmerich, S., Jestädt, H., Klepp, S., Million, A., & Zinke, C. (2022). Bildungslandschaften in Campus-Form aus schulischer Perspektive. *DDS – Die Deutsche Schule*, 2022(01), 46–60. <https://doi.org/10.31244/ddS.2022.01.05>
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed). L. Erlbaum Associates.
- Cummings, C., Great Britain, & Department for Education and Skills. (2007). *Evaluation of the full service extended schools initiative, final report*. DfES Publications.
- Dedering, K. (2007). *Schulische Qualitätsentwicklung durch Netzwerke: Das Internationale Netzwerk Innovativer Schulsysteme (INIS) der Bertelsmann Stiftung als Beispiel* (1. Aufl). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.
- Earl, L., Katz, S., Elgie, S., Ben Jaafar, S., & Foster, L. (2006). *How networked learning communities work*. Aporia Consulting.
- Educational Landscapes Switzerland. (2017). *Jacobs Foundation*. <https://jacobsfoundation.org/activity/educational-landscapes/>
- Eisner, N. L., Murray, A. L., Eisner, M., & Ribeaud, D. (2019). A practical guide to the analysis of non-response and attrition in longitudinal research using a real data example. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 43(1), 24–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025418797004>
- Fend, H. (2006). *Neue Theorie der Schule: Einführung in das Verstehen von Bildungssystemen*. VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-90169-5>
- Fischer, F. (2002). Gemeinsame Wissenskonstruktion—Theoretische und methodologische Aspekte. *Psychologische Rundschau*, 53(3), 119–134. <https://doi.org/10.1026//0033-3042.53.3.119>
- Fussangel, K. (2008). *Subjektive Theorien von Lehrkräften zur Kooperation Eine Analyse der Zusammenarbeit von Lehrerinnen und Lehrern in Lerngemeinschaften* [Universität Wuppertal, Fakultät für Human- und Sozialwissenschaften» Erziehungswissenschaften» Dissertationen]. <http://elpub.bib.uni-wuppertal.de/edocs/dokumente/fbg/paedagogik/diss2008/fussangel>
- Fussangel, K., & Dizinger, V. (2014). *The challenge of change? The development of all-day schools and its implications for teacher stress*. The Challenge of Change.
- Fussangel, K., & Gräsel, C. (2012). Lehrerkooperation aus der Sicht der Bildungsforschung. In E. Baum, T.-S. Idel, & H. Ullrich (Hrsg.), *Kollegialität und Kooperation in der Schule: Theoretische Konzepte und empirische Befunde* (S. 29–40). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-94284-1_2
- Gräsel, C., Fußangel, K., & Pröbstel, C. (2006). Lehrkräfte zur Kooperation anregen—Eine Aufgabe für Sisyphos? *Zeitschrift Für Pädagogik*, 52(2), 205–219.
- Granrud, M. D., Anderzén-Carlsson, A., Bisholt, B., & Steffenak, A. K. M. (2019). Public health nurses' perceptions of interprofessional collaboration related to adolescents' mental health problems in secondary schools: A phenomenographic study. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 28(15-16), 2899–2910. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.14881>
- Griffiths, A.-J., Alsip, J., Hart, S. R., Round, R. L., & Brady, J. (2021). Together we can do so much: A systematic review and conceptual framework of collaboration in schools. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 36(1), 59–85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0829573520915368>
- Grimm, K. J., Ram, N., & Estabrook, R. (2017). *Growth modeling: Structural equation and multilevel modeling approaches*. Guilford Publications.
- Grosche, M., Fussangel, K., & Gräsel, C. (2020). *Kokonstruktive Kooperation zwischen Lehrkräften. Aktualisierung und Erweiterung der Kokonstruktionstheorie sowie deren Anwendung am Beispiel schulischer Inklusion*. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:25803>
- Halbheer, U., Kunz, A., & Maag Merki, K. (2008). Kooperation zwischen Lehrpersonen in Zürcher Gymnasien. Eine explorative Fallanalyse zum Zusammenhang zwischen kooperativ-reflexiven Prozessen in Schulen und schulischen Qualitätsmerkmalen. *Zeitschrift für Soziologie der Erziehung und Sozialisation*, 28(1), 19–35.
- Harris, A., Chapman, C., Muijs, D., Russ, J., & Stoll, L. (2006). Improving schools in challenging contexts: Exploring the possible. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 17(4), 409–424. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450600743483>
- Hartmann, U., Richter, D., & Gräsel, C. (2021). Same Same But Different? Analysen zur Struktur kollegialer Kooperation unter Lehrkräften im Kontext von Schul- und Unterrichtsentwicklung. *Unterrichtswissenschaft*, 49(3), 325–344. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42010-020-00090-8>
- Hillebrand, A., Webs, T., Kamarianakis, E., Holtappels, H. G., Bremm, N., & van Ackeren, I. (2017). *Schulnetzwerke als Strategie der Schulentwicklung: Zur datengestützten Netzwerkzusammenstellung von Schulen in sozialräumlich deprivierter Lage*. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:12971>
- Holzberger, D., & Schiepe-Tiska, A. (2021). Is the school context associated with instructional quality? The effects of social composition, leadership, teacher collaboration, and school climate. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 32(3), 465–485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2021.1913190>
- Hord, S. M. (1997). *Professional learning communities: Communities of continuous inquiry and improvement*. Southwest Educational Development Laboratory. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED410659>
- Howardson, G. N., Karim, M. N., & Horn, R. G. (2017). The latent change score model: A more flexible approach to modeling time in self-regulated learning. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 32(3), 317–334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-016-9475-4>
- Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>

- Huber, S. G. (2014). Kooperation in Bildungslandschaften. Aktuelle Diskussionsstränge, Wirkungen und Gelingensbedingungen. In S. G. Huber (Hrsg.), *Kooperative Bildungslandschaften. Netzwerke(n) im und mit System* (S. 3–29). Link u.a.
- Huber, S. G., Kilic, S., Schwander, M., & Wolfram, C. (2014). Bildungslandschaften—Übersicht über exemplarische Projekte und Evaluationen. In S. G. Huber (Hrsg.), *Kooperative Bildungslandschaften. Netzwerke(n) im und mit System* (S. 137–164). Link u.a.
- Huber, S. G., Werner, R., Koszuta, A., & Schwander, M. (2021). Programm «Bildungslandschaften Schweiz»: Strategische Allianzen zur Gestaltung von Bildungsbiografien. *Infonium*, 1, 3–4.
- Järvinen, H., Sendzik, N., Sartory, K., & Otto, J. (2015). Unterstützungssysteme im Kontext von Regionalisierungsprozessen. Eine theoretische und empirische Annäherung. *Journal for Educational Research Online*, 7(1), 94–124. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:11049>
- Jopling, M. (2005). *Systematic review: The impact of networks on pupils, practitioners, organisations and the communities they serve*. https://www.academia.edu/1763858/Systematic_review_The_impact_of_networks_on_pupils_practitioners_organisations_and_the_communities_they_serve
- Kalinowski, E., Jurczok, A., Westphal, A., & Vock, M. (2022). Welche individuellen und institutionellen Faktoren begünstigen die Kooperation von Grundschullehrkräften? *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft*, 25(4), 999–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11618-022-01081-4>
- Kilbane, J. F. Jr. (2009). Factors in sustaining professional learning community. *NASSP Bulletin*, 93(3), 184–205. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192636509358923>
- Koranyi, F., & Kolleck, N. (2017). The role of out-of-school organizations in German regionalization programs: A qualitative content analysis of opportunities for participation. *Journal for Educational Research Online*, 9(3), 141–166.
- Koszuta, A. (2025). Wie werden Bildungslandschaften in der Schweiz gestaltet und umgesetzt, um Bildungsungleichheit zu reduzieren? Praxen der Ausgestaltung von Bildungslandschaften. *Swiss Journal of Educational Research*, 47(1), 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.24452/sjer.47.1.3>
- Koszuta, A., Werner, R., & Huber, S. G. (2021). Aktivitäten von Akteuren in Schweizer Bildungslandschaften – Welchen potenziellen Beitrag zu mehr Chancengerechtigkeit könnten sie leisten? *Zeitschrift Für Bildungsforschung*, 11(2), 255–270. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s35834-021-00304-8>
- Latta, A. (2023). *Teacher Reflection, agency, adult learning, and equity consciousness in a professional learning community*. ProQuest LLC (2901456477; ED634185). ERIC. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/teacher-reflection-agency-adult-learning-equity/docview/2901456477/se-2?accountid=27469>
- Leclerc, M., Moreau, A. C., Dumouchel, C., & Sallafranque-St-Louis, F. (2012). Factors that promote progression in schools functioning as professional learning community. *International Journal of Education Policy & Leadership*, 7(7), 1–14.
- Lehmpfuhl, U., & Pfeiffer, H. (2008). Regionale Schul- und Bildungslandschaften in den 19 am Modellvorhaben beteiligten Regionen. In H. G. Holtappels, K. Klemm, & H.-G. Rolff (Hrsg.), *Schulentwicklung durch Gestaltungsautonomie. Ergebnisse der Begleitforschung zum Modellvorhaben „Selbstständige Schule“* (S. 195–223). Waxmann.
- Lieberman, A., & Mace, D. H. P. (2009). The role of “accomplished teachers” in professional learning communities: Uncovering practice and enabling leadership. *Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice*, 15(4), 459–470.
- Little, J. W. (2003). Inside teacher community: Representations of classroom practice. *Teachers College Record: The Voice of Scholarship in Education*, 105(6), 913–945. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9620.00273>
- Little, T. D. (2013). *Longitudinal structural equation modeling* (S. xxii, 386). The Guilford Press.
- Lohre, W. (2007). Über das Netzwerk hinaus – Entwicklung und Steuerung lokaler Bildungslandschaften. In C. Solzbacher & D. Minderop (Hrsg.), *Bildungsnetzwerke und Regionale Bildungslandschaften. Ziele und Konzepte, Aufgaben und Prozess* (S. 43–50). Link-Luchterhand.
- Lucas, R. E. (2023). Why the cross-lagged panel model is almost never the right choice. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 6(1), 25152459231158378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459231158378>
- Luder, R., Kunz, A., & Felkendorff, K. (2017). *Integrative Förderung in der Schweiz. Wissenschaftlicher Schlussbericht, Zusammenfassung der wichtigsten Ergebnisse für die teilnehmenden Schulen*. Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich.
- Lütje-Klose, B., & Urban, M. (2014). Professionelle Kooperation als wesentliche Bedingung inklusiver Schul- und Unterrichtsentwicklung. Teil 1: Grundlagen und Modelle inklusiver Kooperation. *Vierteljahresschrift Für Heilpädagogik Und Ihre Nachbargebiete*, 83(2), 112. <https://doi.org/10.2378/vhn2014.art09d>
- Maag Merki, K., & Steinert, B. (2006). Die Prozessstruktur von teilautonomen Schulen und ihre Effektivität für die Herstellung optimaler Lernkontexte für schulische Bildungsprozesse. *Swiss Journal of Educational Research*, 28(S), 103–122. <https://doi.org/10.24452/sjer.28.S.4759>
- Marty, A. (2022). *Kooperation von Regellehrpersonen und Sonderpädagog*innen in Kindergärten und Primarschulen. Rekonstruktion Subjektiver Theorien*. Waxmann Verlag GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.31244/9783830995098>
- Massenkeil, J., & Rothland, M. (2016). Kollegiale Kooperation im Lehrerberuf. Überblick und Systematisierung aktueller Forschung. In K. Moegling, S. Haderl, & G. Hund-Göschel (Hrsg.), *Was sind gute Schulen? Teil 1. Konzeptionelle Überlegungen und Diskussion* (S. 87–118). Prolog-Verlag.
- Matusik, J. G., Hollenbeck, J. R., & Mitchell, R. L. (2021). Latent change score models for the study of development and dynamics in organizational research. *Organizational Research Methods*, 24(4), 772–801. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428120963788>

- Maykus, S. (2009a). Kooperation: Mythos oder Mehrwert? Der Nutzen multiprofessioneller Kooperation der Akteure schulbezogener Jugendhilfe. In F. Prüss, S. Kortas, & M. Schöpa (Hrsg.), *Die Ganztagschule: Von der Theorie zur Praxis: Anforderungen und Perspektiven für Erziehungswissenschaft und Schulentwicklung* (S. 307–321). Juventa.
- Maykus, S. (2009b). Neue Perspektiven für Kooperation: Jugendhilfe und Schule gestalten kommunale Systeme von Bildung, Betreuung und Erziehung Neue Perspektiven für Kooperation. *Lokale Bildungslandschaften* (P. Bleckmann & A. Durdel, Hrsg.; S. 37–55). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-91857-0_3
- McArdle, J. J., Hamagami, F., Meredith, W., & Bradway, K. P. (2000). Modeling the dynamic hypotheses of Gf–Gc theory using longitudinal life-span data. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 12(1), 53–79. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1041-6080\(00\)00036-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1041-6080(00)00036-4)
- McCullum, C. C. (2017). *An examination of the factors that influence the transfer of learning among K-12 educators participating in professional learning communities*. ProQuest LLC (2011266532; ED5790365, 211). ERIC. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/examination-factors-that-influence-transfer/docview/2011266532/se-2?accountid=27469>
- Milara, I. S., Pitkänen, K., Laru, J., Iwata, M., Orduña, M. C., & Riekk, J. (2020). STEAM in Oulu: Scaffolding the development of a Community of Practice for local educators around STEAM and digital fabrication. *International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction*, 26, 100197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcci.2020.100197>
- Minderop, D., & Solzbacher, C. (2007). Ansätze und Dimensionen – eine Einführung. In *Bildungsnetzwerke und Regionale Bildungslandschaften. Ziele und Konzepte, Aufgaben und Prozesse* (S. 3–13). Link-Luchterhand.
- Moolenaar, N. M. (2010). *Ties with potential: Nature, antecedents, and consequences of social networks in school teams*. Universiteit van Amsterdam [Host].
- Muckenthaler, M., Tillmann, T., Weiß, S., Hillert, A., & Kiel, E. (2019). Belastet Kooperation Lehrerinnen und Lehrer? Ein Blick auf unterschiedliche Kooperationsgruppen und deren Belastungserleben. *Journal for Educational Research Online*, 11(2), 147–168.
- Muckenthaler, M., Tillmann, T., Weiß, S., & Kiel, E. (2020). Teacher collaboration as a core objective of school development. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 31(3), 486–504. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2020.1747501>
- Muijs, D. (2015). Improving schools through collaboration: A mixed methods study of school-to-school partnerships in the primary sector. *Oxford Review of Education*, 41(5), 563–586. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2015.1047824>
- Muijs, D., West, M., & Ainscow, M. (2010). Why network? Theoretical perspectives on networking. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 21(1), 5–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450903569692>
- Muthén, L. K., & Muthén, B. O. (2002). How to use a Monte Carlo Study to decide on sample size and determine power. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 9(4), 599–620. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15328007SEM0904_8
- Neyman, J., & Pearson, E. S. (1928). On the use and interpretation of certain test criteria for purposes of statistical inference: Part I. *Biometrika*, 20A(1/2), 175. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2331945>
- Olivier, D. F., & Huffman, J. B. (2016). Professional learning community process in the United States: Conceptualization of the process and district support for schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 36(2), 301–317. ERIC <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2016.1148856>
- Paulsrud, D., & Nilholm, C. (2023). Teaching for inclusion – A review of research on the cooperation between regular teachers and special educators in the work with students in need of special support. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 27(4), 541–555. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2020.1846799>
- Plauborg, H. (2009). Opportunities and limitations for learning within teachers' collaboration in teams: Perspectives from action learning. *Action Learning: Research and Practice*, 6(1), 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767330902731293>
- Pozas, M., & Letzel-Alt, V. (2023). Teacher collaboration, inclusive education and differentiated instruction: A matter of exchange, co-construction, or synchronization? *Cogent Education*, 10(2), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2240941>
- Pool Maag, S. (2022). Multiprofessionelle Zusammenarbeit an inklusiven Schulen. *Schweizerische Zeitschrift für Heilpädagogik*, 28(5–6), 15–21.
- Putnam, R. T., & Borko, H. (2000). What do new views of knowledge and thinking have to say about research on teacher learning? *Educational Researcher*, 29(1), 4–15. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X029001004>
- Ramukumba, T. S., Rasesemola, R. M., & Matshoge, G. P. (2019). Compliance to the Integrated School Health Policy: Intersectoral and multisectoral collaboration. *Curationis*, 42(1), e1–e8. <https://doi.org/10.4102/curationis.v42i1.1912>
- Reeves, P. M., Pun, W. H., & Chung, K. S. (2017). Influence of teacher collaboration on job satisfaction and student achievement. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.06.016>
- Reinecke, J., & Seddig, D. (2011). Growth mixture models in longitudinal research. *ASTA Advances in Statistical Analysis*, 95(4), 415–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10182-011-0171-4>
- Richter, D., & Pant, H. A. (2016). *LEHRERKOOPERATION IN DEUTSCHLAND*. https://www.telekom-stiftung.de/sites/default/files/files/media/publications/studie_lehrerkooperation_in_deutschland_1.pdf
- Riveros, A., Newton, P., & Burgess, D. (2012). A situated account of teacher agency and learning: Critical reflections on professional learning communities. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 35(1), 202–216.
- Rosenholtz, S. J. (2000). *Teachers' workplace: The social organization of schools* [Nachdr.]. Teachers College Press.
- Santen, E. V., & Seckinger, M. (2003). *Kooperation: Mythos und Realitaet in der Praxis. Eine empirische Studie zur interinstitutionellen Zusammenarbeit am Beispiel der Kinder- und Jugendhilfe*. Deutsches Jugendinstitut.

- Servage, L. (2008). Critical and transformative practices in professional learning communities. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 35(1), 63–77.
- Slavit, D., Kennedy, A., Lean, Z., Nelson, T. H., & Deuel, A. (2011). Support for professional collaboration in middle school mathematics: A complex web. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 38(3), 113–131.
- Spyropoulou, N., & Kameas, A. (2024). Leveraging communities of practice for STEAM education: A study on engagement and professional development. *European Journal of Education*, 59(4), e12806. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12806>
- Steinert, B., & Maag Merki, K. (2009). *Kooperation zwischen Lehrpersonen und Schulen. Empirische Analysen und offene Forschungsfragen*. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:13709>
- Tan, Y. S. M., & Caleon, I. S. (2016). Problem finding in professional learning communities: A learning study approach. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 60(2), 127–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2014.996596>
- Terhart, E., & Klieme, E. (2006). Kooperation im Lehrerberuf: Forschungsproblem und Gestaltungsaufgabe. Zur Einführung in den Thementeil. *Zeitschrift Für Pädagogik*, 52(2), 163–166.
- Thielen, M. (2010). Soziale Arbeit im Kontext Schule. *Zeitschrift Für Sozialpädagogik ZfSp*, 8(1), 3–22.
- Thomas, G., Wineburg, S., Grossman, P., Myhre, O., & Woolworth, S. (1998). In the company of colleagues: An interim report on the development of a community of teacher learners. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 14(1), 21–32. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(97\)00058-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(97)00058-9)
- Thompson, S. C., & McKelvy, E. (2007). Shared vision. Team learning and professional learning communities. *Middle Ground*, 10(3), 12–14.
- Tjosvold, D., West, M. A., & Smith, K. G. (2003). Teamwork and cooperation: Fundamentals of organizational effectiveness. In *International handbook of organizational teamwork and cooperative working* (S. 3–8). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470696712.ch1>
- Trumpa, S., Franz, E.-K., & Greiten, S. (2016). Forschungsbefunde zur Kooperation von Lehrkräften. Ein narratives Review. *Die Deutsche Schule*, 108(1), 80–92.
- Vangrieken, K., Dochy, F., Raes, E., & Kyndt, E. (2015). Teacher collaboration: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 15, 17–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.04.002>
- van Schaik, P., Volman, M., Admiraal, W., & Schenke, W. (2020). Fostering collaborative teacher learning: A typology of school leadership. *European Journal of Education*, 55(2), 217–232. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12391>
- Vescio, V., Ross, D., & Adams, A. (2008). A review of research on the impact of professional learning communities on teaching practice and student learning. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 24(1), 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2007.01.004>
- Warwas, J., Helm, C., & Schadt, C. (2019). Unterstützendes Führungsverhalten schulischer Führungskräfte für die Arbeit professioneller Lerngemeinschaften im Kollegium. *Zeitschrift für Bildungsforschung*, 9(1), 37–70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s35834-019-00230-w>
- Watkins, T. M. (2016). *Professional learning community implementation and teacher perceptions of participation influences on professional growth*. https://www.academia.edu/35093028/Professional_Learning_Community_Implementation_and_Teacher_Perceptions_of_Participation_Influences_on_Professional_Growth_Submitted_by
- Wilbers, K. (2004). *Soziale Netzwerke an berufsbildenden Schulen. Analyse, Potenziale, Gestaltungsansätze*. Eusl-Verl.
- Wood, D. (2007). Teachers' learning communities: Catalyst for change or a new infrastructure for the status quo? *Teachers College Record: The Voice of Scholarship in Education*, 109(3), 699–739. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146810710900308>
- Wu, Y., Cheng, J., & Koszalka, T. A. (2020). Transdisciplinary approach in middle school: A case study of co-teaching practices in STEAM teams. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 9(1), 138–162. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijemst.1017>
- Wu, Z. (2022). Understanding teachers' cross-disciplinary collaboration for STEAM education: Building a digital community of practice. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 46, 101178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.101178>
- Xu, R., DeShon, R. P., & Dishop, C. R. (2020). Challenges and opportunities in the estimation of dynamic models. *Organizational Research Methods*, 23(4), 595–619. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428119842638>
- Zainal, N. H., & Newman, M. G. (2021). Depression and executive functioning bidirectionally impair one another across 9 years: Evidence from within-person latent change and cross-lagged models. *European Psychiatry: The Journal of the Association of European Psychiatrists*, 64(1), e43. <https://doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2021.2217>
- Zech, L. K., Gause-Vega, C. L., Bray, M. H., Secules, T., & Goldman, S. R. (2000). Content-based collaborative inquiry: A professional development model for sustaining educational reform. *Educational Psychologist*, 35(3), 207–217. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326985EP3503_6
- Zetlin, A. G., Macleod, E., & Michener, D. (1998). Professional development of teachers of language minority students through university-school partnership. *Teacher Education and Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of the Council for Exceptional Children*, 21(2), 109–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/088840649802100205>
- Zhang, J., & Zheng, X. (2020). The influence of schools' organizational environment on teacher collaborative learning: A survey of Shanghai teachers Chinese Education & Society, 53(5–6), 300–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10611932.2021.1879553>

Appendix 1: Attrition analysis

In longitudinal studies, there are inevitably non-responses and dropouts in surveys, which leads to a smaller data set and thus to a lower informative value of the study, but also carries the risk of bias (Eisner et al., 2019). Imputation is an alternative to weighting that can be used to correct for non-response (Buuren, 2018). The following attrition analyses were used to check whether our sample exhibits bias due to (a) the exclusion of individuals from the analyses, as they only answered the survey at one measurement time and (b) the full information maximum likelihood (FIML) imputation of missing values used as standard by the MPlus statistical software. This involves comparing personal data with only one measurement time point with personal data with several measurement time points and personal data with two measurement time points with personal data with three measurement time points. Demographic data such as gender, age, professional experience and function as well as motivational aspects of participation in the educational landscape, measured as invested work and leisure time, and subjective assessments of the extent to which the network within the educational landscape improves the exchange of information and experience or increases work motivation are considered.

The groups that took part in only one of the surveys or in several surveys do not differ significantly according to gender and age (see Table A1). There is a significant difference in professional experience ($F = 3.75(2)$, $p = 0.03$): People who have taken part in two surveys show lower values for professional experience. However, the values for people who took part in three surveys are higher again. Consequently, there is no linear correlation, so it can be assumed that the difference in professional experience between the groups came about more by chance.

People who took part in one, two or three measurement time points do not differ in terms of the amount of working time invested, nor is a linear trend visible. The information provided by the participants regarding the amount of free time invested indicates a trend (ANOVA group comparison overall not significant $p = 0.14$), according to which people who (have to) invest more free time took part in fewer surveys. The LSD posthoc test also shows that people who only took part in one measurement point invested significantly ($p = 0.05$) more free time than those who took part in three measurement points. Thus, the degree to which the participants had to sacrifice their free time to participate in the educational landscape is a possible reason for not participating in further surveys that require additional time.

With regard to motivational aspects, namely the assessment of whether the network within the educational landscape increases job satisfaction on the one hand and improves the exchange of ideas and experiences between school and non-school stakeholders on the other, there are no significant differences between the groups. The mean values are almost identical.

With the exception of the information regarding invested free time, our sample does not indicate any systematic distortions with regard to dropouts and missing data. Since no motivational differences in the assessments of the effectiveness of the networks can be identified despite differences in the amount of free time invested, we see no problems in using the data for the planned analyses.

Table A1. Comparison of personal and motivational variables for participants with one or more survey filled out.

Measurement points	1	2	3
<i>N</i>	527	237	101
%	60.9	27.4	11.7
Female	69%	69%	67%
Mean age (SD)	44.90 (10.82)	46.06 (10.67)	46.94 (9.85)
Mean work experience (SD)	9.88 (9.90)	6.63 (6.09)	7.91 (7.78)
Working time spent	2.90 (3.73)	3.29 (3.95)	2.74 (3.91)
Free time spent	2.21 (2.78)	2.01 (3.00)	1.60 (1.08)
Improves exchange of information and experiences	3.32 (0.72)	3.43 (0.61)	3.41 (0.43)
Increases work motivation	3.05 (0.78)	3.06 (0.68)	3.05 (0.53)

Table A2. Measurement invariance professional exchange.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	76.42	51	0.06	0.93
Metric	Loading only	80.40	57	0.05	0.94
Scalar	Loading and Intercept	88.15	63	0.05	0.94

Table A3. Measurement invariance joint work organization.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	74.97	51	0.06	0.95
Metric	Loading only	79.70	57	0.05	0.95
Scalar	Loading and Intercept	85.67	63	0.05	0.95

Appendix 2: Measurement invariance of instruments

A scalar measurement invariance can be assumed (see Table A2) for the dimension of professional exchange (Fussangel, 2008): The χ^2 -differences are not significant and the changes in the fit characteristics for the metric and scalar model are within the specified limits (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). The improvement in the RMSEA and CFI parameters can be explained by random variation in small samples (Muthén & Muthén, 2002).

A scalar measurement invariance can be assumed (see Table A3) for the dimension of joint work organization (Fussangel, 2008): The χ^2 -differences are not significant and the changes in the fit indices for the metric and scalar model are within the specified limits (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). The improvement and RMSEA and CFI scores can be explained by random variation in small samples (Muthén & Muthén, 2002).

To ensure the measurement invariance of the co-construction dimension (Fussangel, 2008) across the time points, correlations between the error terms of the three measurement time points were specified for all items in the configural, metric and scalar models. These correlations can be justified on the basis of theoretical considerations and empirical findings: It can be assumed that an item that is measured several times over time has the same (systematic) proportions in the error variance in each case. From an empirical perspective, the models showed a significantly improved fit to the data by adding the correlations to account for systematic sources of error, which was confirmed by the fit indices (CFI, RMSEA). The characteristics of the measurement invariance show a mixed picture (see Table A4): The χ^2 -differences are not significant, but the changes in the fit parameters for the metric and scalar models are outside the specified limits, with the exception of the decrease in the RMSEA of the metric model (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). If the factor loadings and the intercept for the item 'It happens that I have my planning of offers critically and constructively evaluated by colleagues in the educational landscapes project' are removed, all fit parameters are within the specified limits. The free estimate of the item can be plausibilized by the fact that no more offers were planned at the third measurement point. Accordingly, there is partial scalar invariance for co-construction. This means that the structure of the latent variable is largely comparable across the measurement points, although there are differences in the specific item on planning offers.

Scalar measurement invariance can be assumed for the dimension workload reduction (see Table A5): The χ^2 -differences are not significant and the changes in the fit parameters for the metric and scalar models are within the specified limits (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). The improvement of RMSEA and CFI can be explained by random variation in small samples (Muthén & Muthén, 2002).

For the emotional relief dimension correlations between the error terms of the three measurement times were specified for all items in the configural, metric and scalar models justified by theoretical considerations and empirical findings (see above). Scalar measurement invariance can be assumed for the emotional relief-scale (see Table A6): The χ^2 -differences are not significant and the changes in the fit parameters for the metric and scalar models are within the specified limits (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). The improvement of RMSEA and CFI can be explained by random variation in small samples (Muthén & Muthén, 2002).

Scalar measurement invariance can be assumed for the dimension professionalization (see Table A7): The χ^2 -differences are not significant and the changes in the fit parameters for the metric and scalar models are within the specified limits (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). The improvement of RMSEA and CFI can be explained by random variation in small samples (Muthén & Muthén, 2002).

Table A4. Measurement invariance co-construction.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	38.58	39	0.00	1.00
Metric (strict)	Loading only	48.52	45	0.02	0.99
Scalar (strict)	Loading and Intercept	60.94	51	0.04	0.96
Metric (partial)	Loading only	41.93	43	0.00	1.00
Scalar (partial)	Loading and Intercept	43.23	47	0.00	1.00

Fixed for Items 1, 2 and 4, free estimation for Item 3.

Table A5. Measurement invariance workload reduction.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	26.260	24	0.023	0.982
Metric	Loadings only	30.898	28	0.025	0.976
Scalar	Loadings and Intercept	32.867	32	0.013	0.993

Table A6. Measurement invariance emotional relief.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	68.873	39	0.067	0.923
Metric	Loadings only	70.462	45	0.057	0.934
Scalar	Loadings and Intercept	75.263	51	0.052	0.937

Table A7. Measurement invariance professionalization.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	31.319	24	0.042	0.984
Metric	Loadings only	35.934	28	0.041	0.983
Scalar	Loadings and Intercept	39.041	32	0.036	0.985

Table A8. Measurement invariance improved focus on students.

Measurement invariance	Fixation	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI
Configural	Without	71.588	48	0.053	0.956
Metric	Loadings only	78.548	56	0.048	0.958
Scalar	Loadings and Intercept	89.159	62	0.050	0.950

To ensure measurement invariance across time points for the dimension improved focus on students, correlations between the error terms of Item 1 and Item 2 were specified in the configural, metric, and scalar models. This can be justified from a theoretical perspective, as both items focus on the direct benefit for the students. From an empirical perspective, the models showed a significantly improved fit to the data by adding the correlations. The loadings of these correlations were also fixed in the metric and scalar models. Scalar measurement invariance can be assumed for the scale (see Table A8): The χ^2 -differences are not significant and the changes in the fit parameters for the metric and scalar models are within the specified limits (Chen, 2007; Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). The improvement of RMSEA and CFI can be explained by random variation in small samples (Muthén & Muthén, 2002).